

**Code of Conduct
for the
Co-Governance
of Pedieos River Linear Park,
NBS Pilot Project**

Our Shared Journey

Within the Pedieos River Linear Park, a valued natural corridor through Nicosia, a unique opportunity emerged to collaboratively develop and govern a dedicated pilot area, specifically entrusted to our community by the Municipality of Strovolos. This pilot area is envisioned not only as a vibrant community space, but also as an innovative showcase for Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), aimed at protecting, enhancing, and respecting local biodiversity, while redefining the human-nature relation within the local community.

Our journey toward this collaborative vision began through a series of co-diagnostic sessions, workshops, and discussions facilitated by the TRANS-lighthouses project. From the outset, these interactions have been inclusive, involving diverse voices from local residents, community groups, municipal representatives, environmental experts, NGOs, schools, and academia. Together, we identified shared aspirations, such as enhancing community interaction, protecting the ecological integrity of the area, ensuring inclusive access, and fostering environmental stewardship.

Throughout this journey, we engaged in processes of dialogue, learning, and unlearning, enabling us to reflect upon traditional governance methods and embrace new, inclusive ways of managing our shared spaces. The outcomes of these interactions underscored the value of community-led co-governance and highlighted the need for innovative approaches such as participatory decision-making, citizen science initiatives, and ecological representation to effectively balance ecological conservation with social benefits.

This Code of Conduct represents the next step in our collective journey. It formally captures our commitment to transitioning toward a participatory co-governance model for this dedicated pilot area, clearly defining the principles, responsibilities, and expectations for all stakeholders involved. The initiative was originally launched by The Cyprus Institute through its involvement in the TRANS-lighthouses project, and the Institute will continue to guide and oversee implementation efforts until the conclusion of the project in October 2026. Following the successful implementation of the pilot, including the co-design of the space, introduction of ecological innovations, and development of a formal co-governance framework, this Code of Conduct also serves as an open invitation for all community members to engage actively in the continued stewardship and shared governance of the space.

Together, we aim to ensure that this pilot area becomes an exemplary model of collaboration, ecological sensitivity, and vibrant community life, providing lessons and inspiration for broader initiatives across Strovolos and beyond.

Description of Space: The pilot area is a quiet, undeveloped field located just a few meters from the Strovolos Municipality building and adjacent to the Pedieos River Linear Park. Nestled within a grove of mature eucalyptus trees, whose presence will be fully respected and preserved, the site offers a unique blend of urban proximity and natural serenity.

This space holds significant potential to become a welcoming, inclusive, and ecologically sensitive environment for community interaction, creativity, learning, and rest. Through the TRANS-lighthouses project, this area will serve as a pilot site for testing innovative NBS and for initiating a co-governance model rooted in local participation, ecological respect, and shared stewardship.

The ultimate vision for the transformation of this space such as its design, functions, and identity will be co-created with participating stakeholders, neighbours, and residents. This process will ensure that the area not only reflects the needs and values of the local community but also supports biodiversity, climate resilience, and a shared sense of place.

Location (coordinates): 35°08'34.4"N 33°20'21.0"E

Map:

Name:

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Shared Values and Principles

Our collaboration in the Pedieos Community Pilot Area is grounded in a shared set of values and guiding principles. These principles help us work together transparently and effectively, ensuring our actions align with the collective vision we have established for our space. While several core values have already emerged clearly during our journey, additional values and their precise definitions will be collectively finalized in our upcoming discussions.

Core Values & Principles (Established)

- **Inclusiveness and Equity:** All voices, regardless of age, gender, background, or expertise, should be heard and respected. The co-governance process should actively seek to include underrepresented groups and ensure fair participation.
- **Transparency:** Information about decision-making processes, budgets, responsibilities, and outcomes should be openly shared. Meeting minutes, design drafts, and implementation updates should be accessible to all stakeholders.
- **Collaboration and Mutual Respect:** Working together means respecting the ideas, time, and input of others. Constructive dialogue, openness to feedback, and shared responsibility are essential elements for co-creation.
- **Shared Learning and Capacity Building:** The co-governance process is also a learning journey. Space should be created for mutual education, skill development, and knowledge exchange; especially on environmental stewardship and democratic participation.
- **Long-term Commitment and Stewardship:** Stakeholders should enter this agreement with a long-term view. This includes care for the space, its biodiversity, and the community, as well as supporting its sustainability and resilience over time.
- **Flexibility and Adaptability:** The pilot area and its use may evolve. The governance process should be able to adapt based on what is learned, the needs of the community, and environmental changes, ensuring responsiveness over time.
- **Recognition of Nature's Rights:** Decisions should take into account the intrinsic value of nature, not only its utility to humans. NBS should respect and enhance biodiversity, ecological function, and the living character of the area.
- **Legitimacy and Trust:** Legitimacy arises when decisions are made through fair, inclusive, and transparent processes. Building trust among all parties is a foundational aspect of this process.
- **Place-based Identity and Cultural Respect:** The space holds cultural, environmental, and social meaning. Its governance should reflect and respect local heritage, knowledge, and community identity.

Additional Values & Principles (To be co-created)

The below space is intentionally left open. Together, during our next collaborative session, we will discuss, define, and finalize any additional core values important to our community.

Roadmap: Our Pathway Toward Co-Governance

The journey toward establishing a thriving, co-governed community and ecological space within our pilot area involves several distinct yet interconnected phases. Some have already been successfully completed through collective effort, while others will follow as we continue working together. Below, we outline these phases, illustrating clearly where we have been, where we are now, and the steps ahead.

Phase 1: Building the Foundations

This initial phase was about getting to know each other, understanding our community's needs, and identifying shared values and aspirations. Together, we:

- Conducted initial stakeholder mapping and outreach.
- Organized participatory workshops and community forums to gather diverse perspectives.
- Undertook co-diagnostic sessions to assess the strengths, opportunities, and challenges within the pilot area.
- Engaged in creative exercises, storytelling, and dialogues that helped us identify common ground and build mutual trust.

Phase 2: Creating Shared Visions

During this stage, we collaboratively developed a clear, collective vision of what our community space could become, emphasizing inclusivity, sustainability, and biodiversity protection. We:

- Defined common goals and core principles for the pilot area's use and governance.
- Identified priority ecological innovations (NBS) suitable for enhancing the area's biodiversity and resilience.
- Mapped preliminary ideas for physical design, activities, and ecological management practices, ensuring they reflected community input and environmental best practices.

Phase 3: Establishing Our Co-Governance Framework

We are currently entering the critical phase of formalizing our shared governance structure. This Code of Conduct is the first formal step toward this goal. In this phase, we will:

- Jointly define roles, responsibilities, and decision-making processes in detail.
- Develop communication protocols and conflict resolution methods.
- Clearly articulate how the "voice of nature" will be embedded within our decision-making processes.
- Finalize and sign this Code of Conduct, affirming our collective commitment.

Phase 4: Co-Designing and Implementing Our Community Space

Once our governance framework is firmly established, we will move forward into the collaborative co-design and implementation of our community space. This exciting phase will involve:

- Co-design workshops and participatory planning activities that engage stakeholders directly in shaping the space.
- Implementing practical NBS to enhance local biodiversity, resilience, and ecological health.
- Developing and piloting community programs, educational activities, and events aimed at fostering a sense of community ownership and stewardship.

Phase 5: Continuous Collaboration, Reflection, and Improvement

Our co-governance journey will not end with implementation. To sustain and enhance our achievements, we will commit to ongoing collaboration, learning, and improvement, including:

- Regular community meetings to review progress, gather feedback, and refine our approach.
- Transparent monitoring of social and ecological outcomes through citizen science and participatory evaluations.
- Continually welcoming new members and stakeholders into our governance structure, ensuring inclusivity and adaptability.

Management and Maintenance of the Space

The pilot space is not only a site of innovation and community gathering, it is a living system that requires ongoing care, respect, and collective attention. Management and maintenance are essential components of our co-governance model, ensuring that the space remains welcoming, functional, and ecologically resilient over time.

A Co-Governed Maintenance Framework

Aligned with the roles and responsibilities outlined in a subsequent section, maintenance and management will follow a coordinated framework. While roles will be clearly defined, ensuring accountability and operational clarity, they will also remain adaptable to accommodate different levels of commitment, capacity, and evolving needs.

A designated Maintenance Coordination Group (to be formed and agreed upon by signatories) will:

- Coordinate needs such as light maintenance (e.g. waste removal, watering, cleaning); ecological care (e.g. pruning, soil health, biodiversity monitoring); infrastructure upkeep (e.g. seating, shade elements, signage)
- Set maintenance schedules
- Allocate tasks equitably across involved parties
- Liaise with the Municipality when technical or infrastructural support is required

This structure respects the principle of shared but organized responsibility, ensuring no one party bears the full burden and all involved are recognized for their contribution.

Participation and Rotation

While tasks may be assigned, participation in maintenance activities will be encouraged across all stakeholders. Opportunities for rotating responsibilities (e.g. seasonal care or hosting a clean-up day) will be integrated into the framework to promote inclusiveness and shared ownership.

Youth groups, schools, and community organizations may also be invited to participate in light maintenance or educational care practices, linking community learning with ecological stewardship.

Communication and Responsiveness

A simple reporting mechanism (e.g., shared notice board, WhatsApp group, or feedback sheet) will be set up to flag any issues requiring immediate attention. These will be reviewed by the Maintenance Coordination Group during regular check-ins or co-governance meetings.

Maintenance decisions that go beyond basic care, such as replacing infrastructure or modifying planted elements, will be brought to the wider co-governance body for collective deliberation and approval.

Reflective Learning and Adaptation

Reflections on what works, what doesn't, and what could be improved will be part of the regular governance cycle. Lessons learned will be documented, informing future improvements to the care and management system. This will allow for scaling up or adapting the model to other areas if the pilot proves successful.

Financial Sustainability and Resource Pooling

We acknowledge that maintaining and enhancing the space may at times require modest financial resources whether for repairs, purchasing tools, materials, or implementing small improvements.

To address this sensitively and collaboratively:

- A dedicated discussion space will be opened among signatories to explore appropriate, transparent, and voluntary contributions (in-kind or monetary) that support the space's sustainability.
- Where possible, the community may jointly apply for micro-grants, sponsorships, or local support schemes.
- Tools, materials, and services may also be pooled, shared, or rotated among stakeholders and municipal partners.

These options are not predefined, they are intended to be explored together with openness, fairness, and creativity, allowing different forms of contribution beyond just financial ones.

Booking and Use Management (To Be Explored)

As the space becomes activated, a booking management system may be introduced, particularly to organize shared use of the space for events, workshops, or group activities.

This system:

- Will be co-designed with all parties to ensure openness, accessibility, and fairness.
- May explore low, symbolic fees for certain bookings to support upkeep, only if agreed upon collectively.
- Will include clear principles on how any such funds would be transparently managed and reinvested in the space.

The introduction and governance of such a system will remain open for co-creation, and no financial models will be applied without prior consensus and discussion among signatories.

Institutional Support and Resource Pooling

The Municipality of Strovolos will continue to serve as an important institutional partner. While not assuming full responsibility for care, the Municipality may provide assistance with specialized maintenance, safety inspections, waste management, or infrastructure needs especially where community capacity is exceeded.

Documentation and Data Management

To ensure transparency, continuity, and shared ownership, the co-governance of the Pedieos Community Pilot Area commits to responsible and collaborative documentation and data management practices.

Shared Knowledge and Resource Space

A shared digital repository (e.g., Google Drive or similar) will be maintained to store materials, agendas, notes, decisions, action points, and reference documents relevant to the co-governance process.

- All members of the Action Team will have access to this space and are encouraged to contribute and update materials as appropriate.
- Responsibility for maintaining the structure and organisation of the shared folder will rotate periodically or be assigned voluntarily, based on capacity.

Meeting Documentation and Follow-up

To ensure accountability and progress:

- Each meeting will designate a note-taker responsible for recording key discussions, decisions, and proposed next steps.
- These notes will be uploaded to the shared space and briefly reviewed and validated at the beginning of the next meeting.
- Decisions taken will be tracked in a cumulative document for ease of reference and continuity.

Data Collection and Privacy Compliance

In the course of participatory activities, surveys, or other community engagements, data may be collected (e.g., contact details, feedback, attendance).

- All personal data will be managed in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).
- Data will be used exclusively for the purposes of the project and will not be shared externally without consent.
- Where possible, data will be anonymised and stored securely, and participants will be informed in advance about how their data will be handled.

Roles and Responsibilities

Our successful collaboration depends on clearly defining the roles and responsibilities of each stakeholder involved in managing and governing the Pedieos Community Pilot Area. Clear roles ensure effective collaboration, accountability, and smooth operation of our co-governance framework.

In this Code of Conduct, the term “stakeholder(s)” refers broadly to all individuals, groups, institutions, or organizations with an interest in the space including local residents, schools, community groups, the Municipality, and others. However, stakeholders who formally sign this Code of Conduct commit to an active and ongoing role in shaping, managing, and caring for the space. This group forms what we refer to in this section as the “Action Team” - a collaborative core that guides the co-governance process, contributes to daily and strategic decisions, and helps ensure the shared values and responsibilities are respected.

Below, we provide initial outlines of general roles and responsibilities, while leaving space to finalize and specify details together during our next co-governance meetings.

General Roles (Agreed)

Municipality of Strovolos:

- Provides institutional support, infrastructure assistance, and oversight of public policies affecting the area.
- Ensures alignment with broader municipal objectives and strategic plans.

Community Representatives (Residents, Community Groups):

- Voice local community perspectives, concerns, and aspirations.
- Actively participate in meetings, events, and decision-making processes.
- Promote community engagement and communicate decisions back to the broader community.

Academic Institutions and Researchers:

- Offer expertise on NBS, ecological sustainability, and innovative governance practices.
- Facilitate capacity-building activities and community education.

Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs):

- Provide technical advice, advocacy, and specialized knowledge on environmental protection, social inclusion, and participatory practices.
- Facilitate connections and mobilize additional resources.

Nature Advocates (Ecological Representatives):

- Ensure ecological considerations and biodiversity protection remain central to decisions.
- Monitor and report regularly on environmental impacts and outcomes.

Specific Roles and Responsibilities (To be defined collectively)

The following spaces will be completed collaboratively, outlining specific tasks, responsibilities, and expectations tailored to our pilot area:

Coordination and Facilitation Roles:

1. Project Coordinator

During the co-design and creation of the site, this role will participate in the facilitation team of the workshops to be done, and will participate in the coordination of the team for the implementation of the project.

(Project Management and Coordination) This role will serve as an assisting bridge between the team and the project with the Municipality of Strovolos. The Coordinator will also participate in the development of key documents that may be needed later regarding the operation of the space. The position will also lead the team meetings and take actions towards day-to-day operations. Moreover, Project Coordinator's tasks will also incorporate Internal coordination within the team, representation of the team and the project externally and the monitoring of the implementation of the roadmap guiding the sustainability of the project. Also, the position will be representing the face of the project and be the one who will keep communicating with the municipality.

[To be defined collectively]

Maintenance Roles

1. Site Maintenance Coordinator

Contribution to discussions on materials related to the creation of the space.

Regular site checks, possible clean ups (maybe organize them with the Social Media and Events Coordinator and the Platform Manager as part of voluntary actions with the community: according to the code of conduct), ability to provide advice and action for the nature-friendly maintenance of the space.

[To be defined collectively]

Communication and Outreach Roles:

1. Social Media and Events Coordinator

Communication skills are essential, as is enthusiasm for social media. Documenting the co-design and co-creation process.

The project's social media strategy serves a dual and important role. During the design and implementation phase, it aims to build enthusiasm within the local community for the new space. This approach cultivates a strong sense of ownership among future users and citizens even before the space is officially completed.

Then, once it starts operating, the management of digital media focuses on the systematic promotion of the planned activities and the highlighting of authentic experiences by users. This continuous narrative transforms the physical space into a living community, strengthening its support base among the volunteer management team and the wider public. Dual role of communication strategy: Design phase and operation phase.

2. Platform Manager

Point of Contact, Trusted person who should be known and trusted within the community, so connections can be developed. This person will talk to the users of the space and act as a point of contact. The platform manager can be the voice of the people as through this position, the project can be brought into contact with the people (community). This way, they will be able to convey any issues that arise from users regarding the space to the management team.

[To be defined collectively]

Monitoring and Evaluation Roles:

1. Feedback and Results Evaluation coordinator

Following the citizen science method, the person (team) in this position will be able to use tools to monitor the success of the space (perhaps following a monitoring plan drawn up between Cyl, the Municipality and the team created) and try to facilitate reflection as a way to move forward by adapting and improving the space. The Feedback and Results Evaluation Team can also work with the community liaison, to analyze the surveys and interviews, obtaining and reviewing the results.

2. Community Liaison

Surveys and interviewing

Along with the platform manager, the community liaison person will be responsible for engaging with the users of the space through various interviews or discussions about the use of the space. They will be responsible for creating surveys and distributing them to the users of the space. They may also be the person who can observe and record how the space is used on different days and times. They will work together with the Feedback and Results Evaluation team, as together they will analyze the data and look for the need for new questionnaires or interviews and their topic, based on the needs of the space.

[To be defined collectively]

Decision-Making Processes (To be collectively finalized)

Together, we will clearly define how decisions will be made, the nature of stakeholder voting or consensus processes, and how to ensure equitable participation. Specific details will be agreed upon collaboratively:

Decision-making rules and methods:

[To be defined collectively]

Frequency and structure of meetings:

[To be defined collectively]

Conflict resolution mechanisms:

[To be defined collectively]

External Consultants

In some instances, specific expertise or independent facilitation may be required to support the effective governance, planning, or implementation of the Pedieos Community Pilot Area. To this end, external consultants such as professionals in ecological restoration, participatory facilitation, design, legal matters, or community development may be engaged on a case-by-case basis.

The need for external consultants should be identified collectively by the Action Team during regular meetings, especially when a gap in knowledge, skills, or capacity is recognized. Consultants may be invited to contribute to specific phases (e.g., co-design, ecological assessment, legal advice for agreements) and their role will remain advisory unless otherwise agreed.

When engaging external consultants:

- Their scope of work and timeline should be clearly defined.
- Their engagement should reflect the values and goals set out in this Code of Conduct.
- Where possible, local professionals and community-based experts will be prioritised to ensure contextual relevance and strengthen local networks.
- External contributions must respect the principles of inclusivity, transparency, and accountability.

In all cases, the involvement of external consultants will remain transparent, and their outputs will be shared with the full Action Team. Their participation does not grant them voting rights or decision-making authority unless this is explicitly defined and agreed upon by the group.

Flexibility and Well-being

We recognise that capacity, interest, or circumstances may change. If any member feels uncomfortable or unable to fulfil an assigned responsibility, they are encouraged to:

- Communicate this openly with the rest of the Action Team
- Propose a reallocation or exchange of roles
- Suggest alternative ways they can contribute based on their strengths or availability

The aim is to foster a supportive and collaborative environment where responsibilities reflect not only the needs of the space, but also the interests, skills, and capacities of its members.

Communication and Conflict Resolution Protocols

Clear communication and effective conflict resolution mechanisms are essential for maintaining healthy collaboration and collective decision-making in our community governance structure. This section outlines our general approach, with some specific details to be collaboratively defined in our upcoming meetings.

Communication Protocols (Agreed)

- **Transparency and Regular Updates:** We commit to regularly updating all stakeholders on project developments, governance decisions, and upcoming activities through accessible channels such as community newsletters, digital platforms, and public announcements.
- **Inclusivity and Accessibility:** All communication will be accessible, understandable, and inclusive, considering the diverse needs and preferences of our stakeholders.
- **Active Listening and Respectful Dialogue:** We foster a culture of active listening, respectful interactions, and mutual understanding, ensuring every stakeholder feels heard and valued.

Communication Channels (To be defined collectively)

To ensure effective communication, we will jointly agree on specific channels and practices, including frequency and methods:

Primary communication platform(s):

[To be defined collectively]

Frequency of formal stakeholder meetings:

[To be defined collectively]

Informal communication channels and tools:

[To be defined collectively]

Conflict Resolution Procedures (To be collectively finalized)

We recognize that disagreements and conflicts may arise, and it is essential to manage them constructively and transparently. Together, we will establish a clear and fair conflict resolution process, including:

Steps for raising concerns or grievances:

[To be defined collectively]

Mediation and conflict resolution practices:

[To be defined collectively]

Escalation procedures (if consensus cannot be reached):

[To be defined collectively]

Risk and Mitigation

Co-governance is a dynamic and evolving process that requires mutual understanding, responsibility, and flexibility. This section outlines potential risks that may emerge over time and proposes collaborative approaches to address them constructively, ensuring continuity, accountability, and a supportive environment.

Organisational Change and Transitions

In cases where a member of the Code of Conduct leaves their organisation or is no longer able to participate:

- The departing member is encouraged to propose a suitable replacement from their organisation to maintain continuity and engagement.
- A handover of responsibilities and relevant information should be facilitated by the departing member where possible.
- If a replacement is not proposed within a reasonable timeframe, the Action Team will collectively discuss and agree on how the affected responsibilities may be reallocated.

Disengagement and Ghosting

If a member becomes unresponsive or ceases to participate without explanation:

- A friendly and supportive follow-up will be initiated to check in and understand any underlying difficulties.
- Should non-participation continue without communication, the Action Team may agree to redistribute the member's responsibilities.
- In cases of prolonged disengagement, decision-making rights may be temporarily suspended, following transparent discussion within the team.

Abdication of Responsibilities

When agreed roles or tasks are regularly unfulfilled:

- The Action Team will provide space to raise concerns in an open and respectful manner.
- If no resolution is reached, tasks may be reassigned through shared decision-making and according to availability and capacity.
- These decisions will be guided by fairness, compassion, and the collective well-being of the co-governance process.

Conflict or Misunderstandings

In the event of disagreements or misunderstandings:

- A basic, collectively defined conflict resolution process will be followed, allowing for open expression of views in a safe setting.
- Mediation may be facilitated by a neutral party or subgroup of the Action Team.
- Resolutions will be documented, if necessary, to support transparency and learning.

Resource and Funding Considerations

Ongoing management and potential enhancement of the space may involve financial needs:

- Open, honest discussions will be encouraged around resource requirements and potential solutions, such as shared fundraising or in-kind contributions.
- A future booking management system may be considered as a means of sustaining the space, but only through collective agreement.
- Contributions will always be voluntary, and financial participation will not determine inclusion in decision-making.

Continuous Review and Adaptation

This Risk and Mitigation section, along with the wider Code of Conduct, will be periodically revisited by the Action Team to ensure its relevance and effectiveness, and updated where necessary based on lived experience and emerging challenges.

Changes to the Code of Conduct

This Code of Conduct is intended to remain a living document; one that can evolve to reflect new understandings, changing circumstances, and the experiences of those actively involved in the co-governance of the Pedieos Community Pilot Area.

Requests for changes or updates to this document may be submitted by any active signatory. These requests should be brought forward during a scheduled coordination meeting or submitted in writing to the coordination team in advance. Each proposal will be presented and openly discussed among the members of the Action Team to ensure collective reflection and alignment with shared values.

Decision-making on amendments to the Code will follow a consensus-oriented process. If consensus cannot be reached after discussion, a vote may be conducted where each signatory has one vote. For a change to be adopted, it must be supported by at least two-thirds ($\frac{2}{3}$) of the current signatories, unless a different threshold is agreed upon in advance for specific cases.

All approved changes will be formally recorded and included in the updated version of the Code of Conduct, which will be shared with all members. A transparent log of amendments and their rationale will be maintained as part of the documentation process.

This approach ensures that the Code remains adaptable while upholding the values of inclusivity, transparency, and shared ownership.

Membership, Openness to Future Participation, and Exit

Signing this Code of Conduct signifies active and committed participation in the co-governance of the Pedieos Community Pilot Area. By signing, stakeholders express their agreement with the shared values, principles, and responsibilities outlined in this document, and their dedication to collaborative management and stewardship of this unique community and ecological space.

Commitment Upon Signing

By signing this document, each stakeholder formally commits to:

- Actively participating in co-governance meetings and decision-making processes.
- Upholding and promoting our collectively agreed values, principles, and governance arrangements.
- Contributing constructively to the ongoing design, maintenance, and sustainability of the pilot area.
- Regularly communicating and engaging with fellow stakeholders, fostering trust, transparency, and mutual respect.

Openness to New Members

This Code of Conduct is not a closed agreement but an evolving framework that welcomes new individuals, organizations, and institutions interested in contributing to the co-governance and stewardship of the Pedieos Community Pilot Area. Participation is open to actors from all sectors - academia, government, NGOs, civil society, the private sector, and beyond - who align with the values and principles set forth in this document.

To further encourage broader engagement, existing members are invited to identify and propose potential new participants and to communicate the value of joining the initiative. Engaging new members can be supported by highlighting incentives relevant to their respective missions and interests. Examples include:

- **Academia:** Opportunities to engage in real-world, community-based learning environments; access to co-produced knowledge and citizen science data; collaboration in applied research on sustainability, governance, or ecological restoration.
- **Industry:** Enhanced visibility through association with a socially and environmentally responsible initiative; potential collaboration on green innovation or nature-based technologies; contribution to Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) goals.

- **Government and Municipal Bodies:** Direct engagement with local needs and citizen perspectives; pilot learnings to inform policy development; visibility for supporting inclusive, sustainable urban transformation.
- **NGOs and Environmental Organizations:** A platform for community mobilization and awareness-raising; integration of environmental advocacy with practical co-governance action; visibility and partnership opportunities.
- **Civil Society and Community Groups:** Strengthened voice in shaping local spaces; networking with aligned actors; participation in decisions that directly affect their communities.

These incentives are not exhaustive and will continue to evolve with the needs and priorities of the stakeholders involved. Interested members will be onboarded following the procedures outlined in this Code and shaped through collective agreement.

Procedure for Joining (To be collectively finalized)

To facilitate transparent and inclusive entry into our co-governance framework, we will collectively define clear procedures for new members to join, including:

Expression of Interest:

How potential members formally express their desire to join.

Orientation and Onboarding:

Methods for informing and integrating new stakeholders into our governance structure.

Approval and Confirmation Process:

Steps for formally accepting new members, ensuring alignment with our shared values and principles.

Exit of Members

Participation in the co-governance of the Pilot Area through this Code of Conduct is voluntary and based on mutual respect and shared commitment. At the same time, we recognize that personal circumstances, organizational priorities, or capacity may change over time. Importantly, exiting the Code of Conduct is not seen as a failure or a breach of trust, but as part of the natural evolution of a collaborative process.

This section outlines the principles and process for the respectful and transparent exit of members from this agreement:

Principles

- Exiting the Code of Conduct is a normal part of an evolving co-governance process and will be treated with understanding and respect.
- Members are encouraged to communicate their intention to step back in a timely and transparent manner, to help ensure continuity and to allow space for new participants if needed.
- Exiting members are invited, but not required, to share reflections on their experience, to contribute to ongoing learning.

Process

- A member wishing to exit should notify the broader group of signatories, preferably in writing or at a scheduled meeting.
- The group will acknowledge and formally record the exit, updating the list of active signatories accordingly.
- If the exiting member held a specific role or responsibility (e.g. in maintenance, communication, or coordination), arrangements will be discussed to ensure smooth transition or reallocation of duties.
- In cases of minimum or no notice:
 - The Action Team will collectively review the responsibilities left behind and agree on how to redistribute or cover them in the interim.
 - If the departing member represented an organisation, the team may reach out to that organisation to explore whether someone else is willing to continue the collaboration.
 - Emphasis will be placed on compassion, flexibility, and practical continuity, ensuring that the co-governance process remains inclusive and resilient.

Rejoining

- Members who exit are always welcome to rejoin the agreement in the future, following the Procedure for Joining outlined in this Code of Conduct.

By defining this process, we aim to foster an environment where participation remains meaningful, flexible, and responsive to the needs of the individuals and organizations involved.

Signing Section

We, the undersigned, affirm our commitment to the co-governance of the Pedieos Community Pilot Area, in accordance with the principles, roles, and processes outlined in this Code of Conduct.

Name	Stakeholder Group / Affiliation	Signature	Date

We sign not just to commit to rules, but to a shared purpose. This space is what we make of it - collectively, openly, and with care for people and nature alike.